

Experimental study of heat transfer parameters of serrated plate fin heat exchanger for different materials

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Abstract

The heat transfer and flow friction Characteristics of plate fin surfaces are presented in terms of the Colburn factor j and the Fanning friction factor f verses Reynolds number Re , the relationships being different for different surfaces. The laminar flow model predicts j and f values at low Reynolds number; the data is throughout the range of interest. Velocity and temperature fields have been Computed and j and f factors determined over appropriate range of Reynolds number and geometric dimensions. For this work I have designed heat exchanger according to procedure of design of serrated plate fin heat exchanger [12], Correlation used for finding various heat transfer parameters having Reynolds number less than 200 [6]. Experimental setup was manufactured using calculated parameters of design. The effects of the materials Brass and Copper SPFHE on the heat transfer enhancement and friction factor behaviors in laminar flow regimes ($Re < 200$) are described. The fin dimension of serrated type plate fin heat exchanger SPFHE ($H=3\text{mm}$, $t=0.2\text{mm}$, $s=2.5$, $l_f=5\text{mm}$ for hot fluid and $H=9.5\text{mm}$, $t=0.2\text{mm}$, $s=$, $l_f=5\text{mm}$ for Cold fluid) same for both materials. On this setup readings were taken by varying flow rate of hot oil, at Constant air for different temperatures of selected materials. After getting readings Calculations were done for heat transfer parameters like Reynolds number, Colburn factor and Fanning friction factor.

Introduction

Heat exchangers are devices used to transfer heat between two or more fluid streams having different temperatures. There are many applications of heat exchanger used in industries like power generation, chemical processing, electronics cooling, air-Conditioning, refrigeration and automotive applications. In this work we have examined the results obtained in serrated plate fin heat exchanger for different materials. Heat transfer parameters like Reynolds number, Colburn factor and Fanning friction factor were discussed. In addition, we had examined relation of above heat transfer parameter for different materials and revealed by various graphs.

The flowing fluids in Cross flow serrated type plate fin heat exchanger are hot fluid as oil and Cold fluid as air. Copper and Brass materials were selected for conducting the trials on serrated type plate fin heat exchanger. The Comparative study for these two materials along with heat transfer parameters were carried out. Copper SPFHE have more heat transfer and less friction drop as Compare to brass at various temperatures. So from results select Copper material than brass for more efficiency. After successful Completion of this work it has been decided that Copper material is more efficient than brass material. Also it is seen that as the flow rate of Cold air increases the heat transfer parameter Colburn factor j increases, hence improved heat transfer rate is achieved.

Experimental set up

Photo 1 Experimental Setup

Photo 2 Copper SPFHE, Brass SPFHE

Photo 3 Brass SPFHE

Result and Discussions

Graph1

graph2

Graph.1 show variation of friction factor with Reynolds number for Copper PFHE and Brass PFHE at various temperatures (400C) And Air Flow rates (0.00266m³/s, 0.00248m³/s, 0.00228m³/s). As found, the friction factor increases with increasing Reynolds No. Because as flow rate increases pressure drop also increases. And friction factor proportional to pressure drop. It is observed that the friction factor increases with increasing Reynolds number. Hence as the F increases, the pressure drops also increases accordingly. It is observed that Brass PFHE shows more friction factor as compare to copper PFHE for same flow rate. Experimental results shows friction factor for Brass PFHE are 5% larger than the copper PFHE.

Graph.2 show variation of friction factor with Reynolds number for Copper PFHE and Brass PFHE at various temperatures (450C) And Air Flow rates (0.00266m³/s, 0.00248m³/s, 0.00228m³/s). As found, the friction factor increases with increasing Reynolds No. Because as flow rate increases pressure drop also increases. And friction factor proportional to pressure drop. It is observed that the friction factor increases with increasing Reynolds number. Hence as the F increases, the pressure drop also increases accordingly. It is observed that Brass PFHE shows more friction factor as compare to copper PFHE for same flow rate. Experimental results shows friction factor for Brass PFHE are 6% larger than the copper PFHE.

Graph3

graph4

In Graph 3 it is observed that the Colburn factor decreases with increasing Reynolds number. As the Re increases, the temperature drop also decreases accordingly. It is observed that Copper PFHE at ($q_{\text{air}}=0.00266\text{m}^3/\text{s}$, Hot oil at 400C) shows higher Colburn factor, means higher heat transfer. Brass PFHE at ($q_{\text{air}}=0.00228\text{m}^3/\text{s}$, Hot oil at 400C) shows lower Colburn factor, means low heat transfer. Experimental results shows that for copper PFHE at $q_{\text{air}} 0.00266 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ shows 10 %-16 % greater heat transfer than the Brass PFHE at same conditions .

In Graph 4 it is observed that the Colburn factor decreases with increasing Reynolds number. As the Re increases, the temperature drop also decreases accordingly. It is observed that Copper PFHE at ($q_{\text{air}}=0.00266\text{m}^3/\text{s}$, Hot oil at 450C) shows higher Colburn factor, means higher heat transfer. Brass PFHE at ($q_{\text{air}}=0.00228\text{m}^3/\text{s}$, Hot oil at 450C) shows lower Colburn factor, means low heat transfer. Experimental results shows that for copper PFHE at $q_{\text{air}} 0.00266 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ shows 8 %-10 % greater heat transfer than the Brass PFHE at same conditions .

Conclusions

In this study, the heat transfer Colburn factor j and friction factor f of serrated fins in Copper and Brass air oil serrated plate-fin heat exchangers (SPFHE) were investigated experimentally. The effects of the materials on the heat transfer enhancement and friction factor behaviors in laminar flow regimes ($Re < 200$) are described. The fin dimension of serrated type plate fin heat exchanger SPFHE ($H=3\text{mm}$, $t=0.2\text{mm}$, $s=2.5$, $l_f=5\text{mm}$ for hot fluid and $H=9.5\text{mm}$, $t=0.2\text{mm}$, $s=$, $l_f=5\text{mm}$ for cold fluid) same for both materials. The test was carried out at different temperatures and flow rates of hot fluid at constant flow rate of cold fluid. Key findings of this study were:

- (1) An experimental model is established in this study, which can predict the flow and heat transfer characteristics at low Reynolds number for Copper and Brass materials.
- (2) The Colburn factor j decreases and friction factor f increases with increasing Reynolds number.
- (3) At the same Reynolds number both, the Colburn factor j and friction factor f are larger for Copper SPFHE than Brass SPFHE.
- (4) Friction factor f is temperature independent in SPFHE.
- (5) It is observed that Copper SPFHE at ($q_{\text{air}}= 0.00266 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$, Hot oil at 400C) shows higher Colburn factor as compared with other flow rate ($q_{\text{air}}= 0.00248 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$, $q_{\text{air}}= 0.00228 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$), so more heat transfer is obtained at larger flow rate of cold fluid.
- (6) Copper SPFHE have more heat transfer and less friction drop as compare to brass at various temperatures. So from results select copper material than brass for more efficiency.
- (7) There is a significant offset between trends of serrated fins by obtained existing the empirical correlations and experimental data at $Re < 200$.

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